

Survey on the Persian Gulf Coast

Survey was undertaken in the spring and autumn of 1970 in continuation of earlier research on settlement and trade routes of Southern Iran in the Islamic and earlier periods.¹ Survey was concentrated on four different sections of the Persian Gulf coast, near Bushahr, near Tāhērī, near Gāvbandi, and near Bandar Abbās.

Seventy-seven sites were investigated in the Bushahr peninsula. The earliest, which occupies less than a hectare, has painted pottery characteristic of Early and Late Ubaid together with a well fired straw tempered coarse ware. The largest number of sites, including three of over seventy hectares each, is of Partho-Sassanian and very Early Islamic date. The most characteristic and distinctive artefact on these sites is a solid thrown clay pedestal, generally between 15 and 20 cm. high, with its base flattened and lipped and the top supported on a heavy stem. This artefact, which may have been a lamp stand, is widely distributed on the Persian Gulf coast. A single specimen was found in excavated context in Tepe Yahya Period I.² In contrast to the density of earlier settlement in the Bushahr peninsula, only seven sites, occupying a total area of less than fifteen hectares, have been found dating from the 9th to 14th centuries A.D..

In the region of Tāhērī the remarkable concentration of smaller sites contemporary with the major occupation levels at Sirāf (Period 2), and the comparative paucity of sites both earlier and later serve, as in Bushahr, to emphasize the short lived importance of the area and its port. Twenty-four sites of Sassanian and Islamic date were visited near

Gāvbandi, and twelve, near Bandar Abbās.

Inland, north-east of Bandar Abbās, the districts of Gulashgird, Rudān, and Jiruft were investigated. With the exception of the major site of Shahr-i Daqianus recorded by Sir Aurel Stein and others,³ mediaeval Islamic sites proved rare, although prehistoric and protohistoric occupation was well represented in these areas. In addition to the sites recorded by Stein,⁴ five sites of 5th to 3rd millennium B.C. date were discovered. The largest of these, with pottery paralleled in Tepe Yahya Periods ^{VI-V} (5th to 4th millennia B.C.) covers over nine hectares.

In the town of Khunj, west of Lār, work continued toward the publication of an important group of 14th and 15th century A.D. monuments, comprising a tiled minaret, a Friday Mosque, and two shrines.

It is hoped to complete the survey of the Persian Gulf coast and islands in the winter of 1970, and later to do further work on the most important sites discovered.

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Footnotes

¹ Iran VIII (1970), p. 202-3.

² A drawing is reproduced in G.C. Lamberg-Karlovsky's monograph of the site, in press. Photographs of pedestals in pottery and stone are in A. Iqtidari, Athar-i Shahrshari Pastani-vi Savahil va Khayir-i Khali-i Pars va Darva-yi Uman (Tihzar 1348), pl. 55, 56, 61, 62, 63.

³ Sir Aurel Stein, Archaeological Reconnaissances in North Western India and South Eastern Iran (London 1957), pp. 151-157, plan 16. Keith Abbott, JRGS (1855), p. 47. Sir Percy H. Sykes, Ten Thousand Miles in Persia (London 1902), p. 267.

⁴ Sir Aurel Stein, op. cit., pp. 157-157, 172-180.